

ICT INTEGRATION IN TLE- ENTREPRENEURSHIP INSTRUCTION AT SELECTED MOUNTAIN BARANGAYS

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ICT Integration in TLE- Entrepreneurship Instruction at Selected Mountain Barangays

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Abstract

This research aimed to assess the integration of ICT in TLE- Entrepreneurship Instruction to the Grade VI learners in the Select Public Elementary Schools at the selected Mountain Barangays of Cebu City, Division of Cebu City during the school year 2020-2021. This research employed a correlational method using learners' competency performance. It involved learner-respondents whose demographic profile, test performance, and perception were gathered and statistically treated using average weighted mean, Z-test, and Pearson's R to test the significant difference between ICT applications and test performance. The findings revealed that integration of ICT in TLE-Entrepreneurship Instruction rendered a significant improvement in the academic performance of the students. There was a significant relationship between the test performance and performance. Hence, the enhancement plan for teaching TLE-Entrepreneurship is hereby recommended.

Keywords: *technology and livelihood education, ICT integration, correlational research, entrepreneurship instruction, grade VI learners, selected public elementary schools at the mountain barangays*

Introduction

A country's economy becomes more productive as the proportion of educated workers increases since educated workers can more efficiently carry out tasks that require literacy and critical thinking (Radcliffe, 2020).

ICT includes all digital technology that assists individuals, businesses and organizations in using information. It covers all electronic products that deal with information in a digital form. Therefore, ICT is concerned with digital data storage, retrieval and transmission. (BAU - Beirut Arab University | Information and Communication Technology in Business, n.d.)

Entrepreneurship has played a vital role in the economic development of the expanding global marketplace. Entrepreneurship refers to the concept of developing and managing a business venture in order to gain profit by taking several risks in the corporate world (Editorial team, 2020). Entrepreneurship education aids students from all socioeconomic backgrounds to think outside the box and nurture unconventional talents and skills. It creates opportunities, ensures social justice, instills confidence and stimulates the economy. Entrepreneurship education is a lifelong learning process, starting as early as elementary school and progressing through all levels of education, including adult education (The Knowledge Review, 2016).

DepEd has been monitoring the use of technology in public schools (Mateo, 2019). The use of information and communications technology to support, enhance, and optimize the delivery of information is called ICT. Information and communication technologies (ICT) have become one of the fundamental building blocks of modern society. The Philippines has now regarded the mastering of the basic skills and concepts of ICT as an inevitable part of the core of education. Teachers need to know exactly how ICT is used as a teaching and learning tool, for their purposes and to help students use it.

The findings of the study will be beneficial to Higher Education Institutions to the learners and teachers so that they will be aware of the impact of ICT within the classrooms. It will also help the teachers to cope with the problem in instructions, and to improve their ways of teaching through the help of ICTs.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the performance of the ICT integration in TLE Entrepreneurship Instructions of the Grade VI Learners in the Selected Public Elementary Schools at the Mountain Barangays of Cebu City during the School Year 2020-2021 as a basis for an enhancement plan. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Learners'
 - 1.1.1. age and gender;
 - 1.1.2. technology resources available at home; and
 - 1.1.3. school technology resources?
2. What is the performance of the learners in TLE-Entrepreneurship based on the curriculum guide competencies as to the following:
 - 2.1. recognizing a potential market;
 - 2.2. understanding the market; and
 - 2.3. knowing the importance of marketing mix in the development of marketing strategy?
3. Is there a significant relationship between ICT application and performance?

4. Based on the findings, what entrepreneurship enhancement plan can be developed?

Literature Review

This study presents the related literature and studies that greatly contribute and enrich this study. This review aims to establish a theoretical foundation, highlight existing gaps in the literature, and define key concepts relevant to the research area.

This study is anchored on the theories of Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge, and Technology-Organization-Environment Framework, Learning by Doing, and is anchored to the Republic Act No. R.A. No.10679 Youth Entrepreneurship Act (2014).

This study was anchored on the theory of Tornatzky and Fleischer (1990) the Technology-Organization Environment (TOE) theory. The TOE framework theorizes that technological adoption decision-making. The main variable is influenced by three principal contexts namely; the technological, organizational and environmental.

The adoption of an innovation depends on the pool of technologies inside and outside an organization as well as the perceived characteristics (e.g. relative advantage, compatibility, complex, trainability, and observability) of the innovation. The organizational context are the characteristics and resources of the organization such as managerial support, organizational culture and size, communication processes, and the amount of slack resources an organization has. The environmental context is the setting in which the organization conducts its business. According to the TOE framework the environmental context includes the organization itself, market scope, competitive pressure, technology support infrastructure and regulatory environment.

Several researchers have reviewed literature on the TOE framework. Baker (2012) reviewed studies that had used the TOE framework, noting the type of innovation that was being adopted in each study. He also suggested directions for future research with the TOE framework. He summarized his review as follows: To this point the majority of theoretical development that has taken place related to the TOE framework has been limited to enumerating the different factors that are relevant in various adoption contexts. No new constructs have been added to the framework. Little theoretical synthesis has occurred. Scant critique has been offered. Thus, the TOE framework has evolved very little since its original development.

Lastly, the theory Learning by Doing is a hands-on approach by John Dewey, which enabling the learners to follow their own pace. Dewey believes that encouraging active learning from teachers so that student's talk, write, relate, and apply learning to their daily lives. Learners must make what they learn part of themselves. Teachers need to provide opportunities for active learning, which involves much more than sitting in classes listening to teachers, and memorizing and providing answers. Teachers can have student's film or take picture examples in the community, or, flip the classroom. Putting content, lectures online, and do homework together in class. It feels natural in learning by doing and surprised how effective it can be.

Gaps in the Literature

In establishing a common vision for educational technology, there are always factors to consider in the process of integrating ICT into the teaching and learning. This study will help assess the status of ICT integration in a specific instruction and identify and address key issues emerging that would benefit an institution.

Key Areas for Further Exploration

Teacher's ICT Integration. To further explore teacher integration in ICT, there are areas that are essential for the teaching and learning process. These areas consider the unique demands of the mountain barangays. Are teachers well-equipped and prepared for ICT integration?

Implementation in Teaching. Further exploration of teacher's implementation in teaching. How do teachers use the varied ICT integration in the classroom? Do teachers need to explore ICT using formative and summative assessments?

Student's Academic Performance on ICT Integration. The academic Performance of a student is very important especially since Philippine education needs to produce globally competitive individuals. Are the students ready for the ICT integration in every lesson? Are the students globally ready and competitive? Do we consider students who adopted ICT integration well are globally competitive individuals?

Mountain Barangay Schools. Are the mountain barangays fully equipped with the technology integration? Will the facilities of the mountain barangay schools suffice the needs of the teachers toward the ICT integration? Is there technical support from the local government or community for the ICT integration? These are some of the questions that need to be addressed.

The Need for Actionable Insights

In this connection, it is deemed significant for the administration to ascertain detailed concerns relative to the needs of the learners as to the ICT integration in the mountain barangays. This study aimed to assess the performance of the ICT integration in TLE Entrepreneurship Instructions of the Grade VI Learners in the Selected Public Elementary Schools at the Mountain Barangays of Cebu City during the School Year 2020-2021 as a basis for an enhancement plan.

Methodology

Research Design

The descriptive survey technique was used in the research process. The survey technique, otherwise known as normative survey, is a fact-finding study with adequate and accurate interpretation of the Grade VI learners in the Selected Public Elementary Schools at the Mountain Barangays of Cebu City during School Year 2020-2021.

Respondents

The respondents of the study are coming from 5 elementary schools in the mountain barangays of Cebu City. A total of 156 respondents where in two teachers are coming from Sirao Elementary school, 1 teacher for each of the rest of the identified school and 30 students for each school who have responded to the survey.

Instrument

The main tool for gathering the data was a questionnaire made and framed based on the K-12 Basic Education Curriculum Guide for TLE. However, in some ways, the study gathered data through direct observations and interviews with the respondents.

The questionnaire contained the following: (a) profile of the respondents which includes demographic characteristics of the pupils and teachers; (b) technology resources checklist; and (c) Learning competencies of TLE- Entrepreneurship from DepEd K to 12 curriculum guides.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered, their analysis and interpretations in the light of the specific objectives and hypothesis of the study. Specifically, this presents the data from the five select schools namely; Sirao, Babag, Sibugay, Malubog, and BonBon on the following: demographic profile of the respondents, ICT applications in TLE- Entrepreneurship instruction employed by the teachers, performance of the learners in TLE-Entrepreneurship based on the curriculum guide competencies, significant relationship between ICT application and performance, and the perception of the learners and teachers in the utilization of ICT in TLE- Entrepreneurship instruction. The data analysis was presented in tabular forms followed by textual discussions.

Basic Information Related To Learners

Table 1. *Profile of the Learners as to Age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
19 yrs. old & above	0	0
17-18	0	0
15-16	1	0.67
13-14	7	4.67
11-12	136	90.66
10 yrs. old & below	6	4
Total	150	100

The table above shows that there were 150 learner-respondents. For the 10 and below age group, there were 6 respondents or 4 % of the entire respondent population.

For ages 11-12, there were 136 respondents or 90.66 % of the total number of respondents. As to ages 13-14, there were 7 respondents or 4.67 % of the total population of respondents. As regards, the 15-16 age range, there was one respondent or 0.67 % of the entire population. For the 17-18 age range and the 19-year-olds and above, there were no respondents at all. It implies that 11-12 years old is the majority age of the learners.

Learner-Respondents' Gender

The gender variable categorizes the respondents into male or female. The table that follows shows the respondents' profile on this information.

Table 2. *Learner-Respondents' Gender*

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Male	63	42
Female	87	58
Total	150	100

Table 2 reflects the gender of the respondents as male or female. There were 63 male respondents or 42 % of the entire population while there were 87 female respondents or 58 % of the total population. This means that the majority of the learners are females.

Technology Resources Available at Home

This sub-variable provides information on the learners' technology resources available at their respective homes. The table that follows shows the respondents' profile on this information for the five identified schools.

Table 3. Learners' Technology Resources Available At Home

No	Materials	Frequency Of Available	%	Frequency of Not Available	%	Total Freq.	%
1.	Computer	59	39.33	91	60.67	150	100
2.	Scanner	11	7.33	139	92.67	150	100
3.	Printer	35	23.33	115	76.67	150	100
4.	Multimedia Projector	33	22	117	78	150	100
5.	Interactive CD's	11	7.33	139	92.67	150	100
6.	Audio & Video Discs	28	18.67	122	81.33	150	100
7.	Slides for Power-point Presentations	25	16.67	125	83.33	150	100
8.	Computer Worksheets	20	13.33	130	86.67	150	100
9.	Television	71	47.33	79	52.67	150	100
10.	Radio	53	35.33	97	64.67	150	100
11.	Internet Services	20	13.33	130	86.67	150	100
12.	Smart Phones	58	38.66	92	61.33	150	100
13.	Non-android Mobile Phones	41	27.33	109	72.67	150	100
14.	Audio Speaker	48	32	102	68	150	100
15.	Audio Recorders	30	20	120	80	150	100
16.	Digital Camera/Video Camcorder	26	17.33	124	82.67	150	100
17.	Streaming Media	32	21.33	118	78.67	150	100
18.	Communication Software	20	13.33	130	86.67	150	100
19.	E-book	8	5.33	142	94.67	150	100
20.	Processing Tool	33	22	117	78	150	100

Table 3 presents the technology resources at home. For the technology resources available at home, it runs as follows: there are 59 learners with computers, 11 learners with scanners, 35 learners with printers, 33 learners with multimedia projectors, 11 learners with interactive CD's, 28 learners with audio and video discs, 25 learners with slides for powerpoint presentations, 20 learners with computer worksheets, 71 learners with television, 53 learners with radio, 20 learners with internet services, 58 learners with smartphones, 41 learners with non-android mobile phones, 48 learners with audio speakers, 30 learners with audio recorders, 26 learners with a digital camera/video camcorder, 32 learners with streaming media, 20 learners with communication software, 8 learners with the e-book, and 33 learners with processing tools. Results showed that television has the most available at home due to infographics and videos which are very useful.

School Technology Resources

This sub-variable provides information on the school technology resources. The table that follows shows the overall profile of information on the said sub-variable.

Table 4. School Technology Resources

No	Materials	Frequency Of Available	%	Frequency of Not Available	%	Total Freq.	%
1.	Computer	6	100	0	0	150	100
2.	Scanner	0	0	6	100	150	100
3.	Printer	6	100	0	0	150	100
4.	Multimedia Projector	6	100	0	0	150	100
5.	Interactive CD's	0	0	6	100	150	100
6.	Audio & Video Discs	0	0	6	100	150	100
7.	Slides for Power-point Presentations	6	100	0	0	150	100
8.	Computer Worksheets					150	100
9.	Television	6	100	0	0	150	100
10.	Radio	6	100	0	0	150	100
11.	Internet Services	0	0	6	100	150	100
12.	Smart Phones	0	0	6	100	150	100
13.	Non-android Mobile Phones	6	100	0	0	150	100

14. Audio Speaker	0	0	6	100	150	100
15. Audio Recorders	6	100	0	0	150	100
16. Digital Camera/Video Camcorder	0	0	6	100	150	100
17. Streaming Media					150	100
18. Communication Software	0	0	6	100	150	100
19. E-book	0	0	6	100	150	100
20. Processing Tool	6	100	0	0	150	100

The table reflects the availability of technology resources utilized by the teachers of the select schools. It runs as follows: 6 teachers have available computers, 6 teachers have no available scanners, 6 teachers have available printers, 6 teachers have available multimedia projectors, 6 teachers have no available interactive CD’s, 6 teachers have no available audio and video discs, 6 teachers have available slides for power-point presentations, 6 teachers have available computer worksheets, 6 teachers have available television, 6 teachers have no available radio, 6 teachers have no available internet services, 6 teachers have available smartphones, 6 teachers have no available non- android mobile phones, 6 teachers have available audio speakers, 6 teachers have no available audio recorders, 6 teachers have no available digital camera/video camcorder, 6 teachers have no available streaming media, 6 teachers have no available communication software, 6 teachers have no available e-book, and 6 teachers have available processing tools.

ICT Application in TLE- Entrepreneurship Instruction

This sub-variable provides information on the ICT applications in TLE- Entrepreneurship instruction employed by the teacher. Specifically, it provides data on the following categorization: Microsoft word, Microsoft Excel, Microsoft PowerPoint, use of the internet, and others. The table that follows presents each of the aforementioned categories.

Table 5. *ICT Application in TLE- Entrepreneurship Instruction Employed by the Teacher*

ICT Applications	5	4	3	2	1	Mean
Microsoft Word	3	3	0	0	0	4.5
Microsoft Excel	3	3	0	0	0	4.5
Microsoft PowerPoint	3	3	0	0	0	4.5
Average Mean				4.5		
Interpretation	Expert					

Legend: 4.20-5.00 (Expert), 3.40-4.19 (Advanced), 2.60-3.39 (Intermediate), 1.80-2.59 (Novice), 1.00-1.79 (Fundamental Awareness)

The table above reveals that in terms of the teachers’ use of Microsoft word in TLE- Entrepreneurship instruction, 3 teacher-respondents rated as “expert” while 3 of them rated as “advanced”. For the teachers’ use of Microsoft Excel, 3 teacher-respondents rated as “expert” while 3 of them rated as “advanced”.

Likewise, as to the teachers’ utilization of Microsoft Power-Point, 3 teacher-respondents rated as “expert” while 3 of them rated as “advanced”. The mean score obtained was 4.5 which is verbally described as “expert”.

Performance Of The Learners In TLE-Entrepreneurship

This variable shows the respondents’ performance on the learning competencies in TLE- Entrepreneurship Instruction; namely, recognizing a potential market, understanding the market, and knowing the importance of marketing mix in the development of marketing strategy. The results are presented in a tabular form and analyzed through textual discussions.

Table 6. *Recognizing a Potential Market*

Score	Frequency	Percentage	Category
90-100	51	34	Outstanding
80-89	83	55.33	Very Good
70-79	16	10.67	Good
60-69	0	0	Fair
59 & below	0	0	Poor
Mean		85.88	
Interpretation	Very Good		

Legend: 4.20-5.00 (Outstanding), 3.40-4.19 (Very Good), 2.60-3.39 (Good), 1.80-2.59 (Fair), 1.00 1.79 (Poor)

The mean score obtained was 85.88 which is verbally described as “very good”. Based on the result, the respondents demonstrated a very good performance on the competency.

Table 7 presents the respondents’ performance on the competency for understanding the market. For the score range of 90-100, 20 respondents or 13.33% of the total population attained an outstanding performance. For the score range of 80-89, 78 respondents or 52% of the total population marked a very good performance. For the score range of 70-79, 52 respondents or 34.67% of the total population rated as good. The mean score obtained was 82.78 which is verbally described as “very good”.

Table 7. *Understanding the Market*

Score	Frequency	Percentage	Category
90-100	20	13.33	Outstanding
80-89	78	52	Very Good
70-79	52	34.67	Good
60-69	0	0	Fair
59 & below	0	0	Poor
Mean		82.78	
Interpretation		Very Good	

Legend: 4.20-5.00 (Outstanding), 3.40-4.19 (Very Good), 2.60-3.39 (Good), 1.80-2.59 (Fair), 1.00 1.79 (Poor)

Table 8 reflects the respondents’ performance on the competency for knowing the importance of marketing mix in the development of marketing. For the score range of 90-100, 14 respondents or 9.33% of the total population attained an outstanding performance.

Table 8. *Knowing the Importance of Marketing Mix in the Development of Marketing Strategy*

Score	Frequency	Percentage	Category
90-100	14	9.33	Outstanding
80-89	69	46	Very Good
70-79	67	44.67	Good
60-69	0	0	Fair
59 & below	0	0	Poor
Mean		82.74	
Interpretation		Very Good	

Legend: 4.20-5.00 (Outstanding), 3.40-4.19 (Very Good), 2.60-3.39 (Good), 1.80-2.59 (Fair), 1.00 1.79 (Poor)

For the score range of 80-89, 69 respondents or 46% of the total population marked a very good performance. For the score range of 70-79, 67 respondents or 44.67% of the total population rated as good. The mean score obtained was 82.74 which is verbally described as “very good”.

Table 9. *Summary of Learner’s Performance*

Competency	Mean	Category	Verbal Description
A. Recognizing a Potential Market	85.88	Very Good	The student had answered almost all items correctly and had high mastery of the competency.
B. Understanding the Market	82.78	Very Good	The student answered almost all items correctly and had high mastery of the competency.
C. Knowing the Importance of Marketing Mix...	82.74	Very Good	The student had answered almost all items correctly and had high mastery of the competency.
Average Mean	83.8		
Interpretation		Very Good	

Significant Relationship Between Teachers’ ICT Application and Learners’ Performance

Table 10. *Significant Relationship Between Teachers’ ICT Application and Learners’ Performance*

Variables	Mean	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers’ ICT Applications 4.5 Learners’ Performance	83.8	0.49	0.0	Reject the null hypothesis	Significant Relationship

Table 10 shows the significant relationship between the teachers’ use of ICT applications and the learners’ performance. The computed p-value which is 0.0 represents the probability of rejecting the null hypothesis (Ho). The null hypothesis is stated in such a way that there is “no” relationship between the two variables being tested. Since the associated p-value (significance) is very small (<.05), it indicates that there is a significant correlation between the two variables.

Conclusions

The findings of this study conclude that the integration of ICT in TLE- Entrepreneurship brought about a significant improvement in learners’ achievement and fostered a more positive attitude both to the teacher and learner- respondents in the integration of ICT in the teaching-learning process as stipulated in the results of the survey.

References

Arnseth and Hatlevik, (2012), Integration of Information, Communication, and Technology (ICT). International Journal Educational

Policy, Research and Practice

Burns, T. C., & Ungerleider, C. S. (2003). Information and Communication Technologies in Elementary and Secondary Education. *International Journal Educational Policy, Research and Practice*

Conlon, T., & Simpson, M. (2003). Silicon Valley versus Silicon Glen: the impact of computers upon teaching and learning: a comparative study. *British Journal of Educational Technology*

Dudeney (2010). National ICT policies can serve several functions

Ghavifekr (2012) technology plays a significant issue. *Researchgate Journal*

Gilbert & Hooper, (2017). *Teaching Humanities & Social Sciences*. 5th Edition, ISBN 9780170359350. *International Journal Educational Policy, Research and Practice*

Jones, A. J. (2003). Infusing ICT use within the early years of elementary education. CRPIT '03 Proceedings of the International Federation for Information Processing

Winzenried, et.al. (2010) teachers who have gone through ICT course are more effective in teaching. *Psychology and Education Journal*

Yang and Wang (2012), importance of technical support Netherland, United Kingdom and Malta

Yuan, Y., & Lee, C. (2012). Elementary school teachers' perceptions towards ICT: The case of using magic board for teaching mathematics. *TOJ*.

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